

USING MEDIA IN ENGLISH TEACHING CLASSES

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Abstract: *The article aims to study the actual problem about using media in the classrooms of foreign languages. In the era of globalization and cross-cultural communication it is urgently important to use media in every English teaching classroom. The following article tries to investigate advantages and comes to the conclusion that a foreign language can't stand aside from the usage of media as a common pedagogical task.*

Keywords— Information technology, mass media, language learning, classroom, TV, newspapers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Living in the age of information technology, people are accustomed to an endless stream of new information. In this regard, awareness has appeared in various fields, such as politics, economics and education. All this provides an opportunity to satisfy needs of human being. Every day, people receive new information about what is happening around the world. It can be both written and oral form and the main sources of information are radio, television, newspapers or the Internet, which are combined into one single concept Media. The use of the media in the field of education, namely in foreign language lessons, is increasing every day. With the use of information technology, teachers have the opportunity to use various media to enrich the language environment of their class, help speed up the learning process, improve the mastery of the subject, and increase the interest in this subject. The methodology of teaching foreign languages involves the use of mass media in the educational process as an effective means of teaching oral foreign language communication as a goal and, at the same time, as a natural result of educational activity. The special role of authentic media in the teaching methodology of foreign languages lies in the fact that they bring students as close as possible to real information sources and "immerse" in the world of current events. The use of authentic, self-selected media texts in the classroom has a long tradition. Until recently, these were mostly newspaper and magazine articles. In recent years, television and radio programs, as well as texts taken from the Internet, have been added to the press materials. So we divide the media into visual (periodicals), auditory (radio) and audiovisual (television, documentary films). Modern visual media provides a wealth of material in print as well as digitally using pictures, videos, graphs, etc. to

create a more suitable learning environment. The media provide a huge amount of new material for the teacher, who can easily find information that fits the school curriculum. Also, working with printed material forms children's interest in reading, due to a variety of information, assignments, presentation.

2. MAIN PART

All this as a whole helps the student to achieve both fluent and competent command of a foreign language. The newspaper tells the reader about real-life events and is consonant with many topics of school textbooks. The teacher should only choose the right material that will correspond to the age level of the student and his level of language proficiency. Undoubtedly, it is necessary to take into account the volume, topic, difficulty of understanding the text and many other factors that can have the opposite effect. Here we should also mention that the teacher has a huge responsibility and requires a high dedication and interest during the development of material that should be useful for understanding for students and have a long-term effect. From a methodological point of view, working with a newspaper significantly enriches and revitalizes the educational process, while simultaneously allowing the teacher to solve a wide range of problems, for example: expanding the vocabulary of students, improving conversation skills on various topics, get additional linguistic and cultural information. But, despite the authentic texts, for greater motivation and variety of the educational process, teachers introduce video materials and also audio materials for a foreign language lesson. Video and audio materials help to learn to understand speech by ear, you can also overcome the following educational tasks, for example, such as: considering dialects of the language, gaining new knowledge about the country of the target language, repeating the past vocabulary or vice versa, expanding vocabulary, using video material for the purpose of searching language information and

much more. All this is not only motivation for the child, but also pushes him to delve into the study of a foreign language on his own. In the last decade, the Internet has been gaining more and more popularity. The Internet is a special environment, which is characterized by a special language, special content and it has a large young audience. Due to the peculiarities of a modern person as a visual in the perception of information, teaching a foreign language is increasingly focused on the use of the multimedia language, moving from using multimedia as an auxiliary, illustrative element to multimedia as a teaching tool. Also, the multimedia space for teaching a foreign language has tasks that are not only to systematize and present educational material, but also to visualize the context of the practical use of a specific educational material. Thanks to these tasks, the teacher supports the motivation of students, turns the process of acquiring knowledge into the process of developing language competencies. Since the language of multimedia is multifunctional, it has various ways of conveying information:

- visual (video, picture)
- auditory (audio material)
- oral (speaking)
- written (texts)

At first, for a long time, only printed or dubbed texts were used in teaching a foreign language, but over time, thanks to the Internet, it became possible not only to read and listen to texts, but also to watch videos that make it possible not only to hear speech, but and observe the behavior or facial expressions of the speaker. The advantages of using media resources in the classroom are obvious, but there are also a number of problems that need to be solved. Among them, it is worth highlighting such as the need to combine information from media sources with the material of the school curriculum, changing the habit of learning a language exclusively with the help of textbooks to actively use newspapers and news sites, as well as creating a student-centered learning environment. Thus, it must be said that the media have a number of advantages in teaching a foreign language, both for the teacher and for the student. The media can provide us with the latest news from the countries of the target language, demonstrate interesting regional material, and show feature or educational films. The media provides an opportunity to create various tasks for the lesson that will help you delve deeper into the study of a foreign language. The media have a large number of illustrations, video material, due to which language learning will turn out to be more interesting both in the

classroom and during independent study. However, the path from innovative ideas in teaching theory to their implementation in pedagogical practice turns out to be long and thorny.

3. CONCLUSION

However, it is known that educational institutions are the most inertial social institutions. In addition, today, with some assumptions, it can be argued that the phenomenon of media competence of the secondary linguistic personality has not found proper understanding at the scientific and theoretical level, moreover, the wide and competent implementation of the technology of its formation in the practice of teaching foreign languages in schools and universities does not occur at all or occurs slowly and not systemically. It can be assumed that there are psychological barriers among teachers, namely: unwillingness to change, fear of modern technology, etc. The main thing, as noted by the interviewed respondents, media education does not fit into the already established system of teaching a foreign language, traditional interpretations of the role of mass communication in the learning process and the introduction of media education in the learning process would lead to a radical "breakdown" of the teacher's previous ideas. Probably, one can agree with this to some extent, especially if one considers that the attitude towards media education among teachers is very different. There is a certain polarization of opinions about media education: from unequivocally optimistic to the exact opposite, skeptical negative. As a rule, a significant part of teachers shows adherence to traditional forms and methods of teaching and treats with distrust, and sometimes just hostility, to the idea of introducing media education into the process of teaching a foreign language. In addition, the other side of the problem should be taken into account, namely, the attitude towards media education enthusiasts on the part of heads of educational institutions and colleagues at work. Unfortunately, this attitude can be so negative that it forces the teacher to stop media educational activity or not start it at all. Another reason that hinders the introduction of media education in the process of teaching a foreign language may be the lack of resource support, which implies not only the availability of the necessary technical base, but also the preparation of the teacher for the introduction of media education in the process of teaching a foreign language. The survey showed that, on average, 27.7% of teachers use media materials in their work. Purposeful questioning and

observation of the activities of teachers confirmed our assumption that even in those (few) educational institutions that are sufficiently well equipped with audiovisual, computer equipment, the latter is rarely used in the process of teaching a foreign language for the purpose of media education. To a greater extent, it is used with a unidirectional didactic function, as a technical means of teaching a foreign language.

4. REFERENCES

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